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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOIL AND PLANTS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the mutual interactions existing between plants and soil. It explains the role of soil in the primary physiological processes—photosynthesis and transpiration—that occur during the life activities of plants. The participation of organic substances contained in plants after their death in the biological cycle and its impact on soil fertility are investigated. Furthermore, the role of plants in soil formation processes and the influence of plant root systems on the physical and chemical properties of soil are analyzed from a scientific perspective. The main objective of the article is to demonstrate the significance of plants in the formation of soil fertility and the preservation of ecological balance.*

Keywords: *plant 1, soil 2, water 3, organic substances 4, fertility 5, soil formation 6, root system 7.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются взаимосвязи, существующие между растениями и почвой. Объясняется роль почвы в основных физиологических процессах, происходящих в процессе жизнедеятельности растений — фотосинтезе и транспирации. Исследуется участие органических веществ, содержащихся в растениях после их гибели, в биологическом круговороте и их влияние на плодородие почвы. Кроме того, с научной точки зрения анализируется роль растений в почвообразовательных процессах, а также влияние корневых систем растений на физические и химические свойства почвы. Основная цель статьи — показать значение растений в формировании плодородия почвы и сохранении экологического баланса.*

Ключевые слова: *растение 1, почва 2, вода 3, органические вещества 4, плодородие 5, почвообразование 6, корневая система 7.*

Introduction

Resources in nature are divided into two categories: exhaustible and inexhaustible. Soil, being one of the most important components of nature, occupies a special place among inexhaustible natural resources. In addition to being a habitat for living organisms, especially microorganisms, soil is the fundamental physical and chemical environment for plant development. Properly understanding and protecting the interaction between soil and plants is of great importance for the sustainable development of natural life. Just as soil health affects plant growth, plants, in turn, play a vital role in maintaining the structure and fertility of the soil [5, p. 110–118].

Since ancient times, the classification of plants and their role in nature have been the focus of scientists. The ancient Greek philosopher and botanist Theophrastus classified plants into trees, shrubs, and herbs based on their stem structure [8; 9]. One of the primary functions of plants in nature is the release of oxygen into the atmosphere as a result of the photosynthesis process. This process is considered an essential condition for the respiration of all living beings. Various physiological processes occur during the life activity of plants. One such process is transpiration; plants regulate their body temperature and protect themselves from the negative effects of high temperatures by evaporating excess water through their leaves. Water and minerals necessary for photosynthesis and transpiration processes are absorbed by plants from the soil through their roots [3, p. 210–215].

Main Part

Soil is a complex system consisting of organic and inorganic substances. After completing their life cycle, plants perish, and the organic substances and mineral elements within them mix into the soil, becoming part of the biological cycle. These organic substances positively influence the increase

of fertility, which is one of the fundamental properties of soil. Soils rich in organic matter are typically dark-colored and characterized by high productivity [6, p. 45–50].

Plants play a crucial role in the soil formation process. Particularly, perennial plants are one of the primary factors in the formation of soil cover in forest ecosystems. In these plants, a certain portion of the biomass (leaves, branches, fruits, bark, etc.) falls onto the soil surface annually as forest litter and decomposes over time, leading to the enrichment of the soil with organic matter. The course of the soil formation process varies depending on climatic conditions, vegetation cover, the composition of parent rocks, and the hydrothermal regime of the soil [5, p. 240–245].

Plants, especially tree-like plants, significantly influence the physical properties of the soil. The root system of plants develops toward the deeper layers of the soil, creating conditions for its loosening and aeration. The cavities created by the root system within the soil allow water and air to move more freely through the soil layers. Simultaneously, roots interact with soil microorganisms to accelerate the decomposition of organic matter and facilitate the absorption of nutrients by plants. The physical structure of the soil directly affects the root development of plants; excessively dense soils limit normal root development, causing plants to weaken and sometimes leading to root rot [2, p. 55–60].

The pH level of the soil also plays an important role in plant development. For most plants, neutral or slightly acidic soils are more favorable, as nutrient absorption occurs more efficiently under these conditions [7, p. 120–125]. Plants are also of great importance in soil conservation. Plants with strong root systems reinforce the soil surface, preventing erosion processes. Grasses, shrubs, and trees exert varying degrees of protective influence on the soil. Leguminous plants, in particular, play a vital role in increasing soil fertility. Rhizobium bacteria living in the roots of these plants fix atmospheric nitrogen, increasing nitrogen reserves in the soil, which subsequently enhances soil productivity [1, p. 85–90; 4, p. 150–155]. The mechanical composition of the soil is another key factor affecting plant development. While sandy soils drain water quickly, clayey soils retain more water. Therefore, the optimal soil type for plants possesses both good water-holding capacity and sufficient nutrients.

Table 1

The Impact of Plants on Soil Properties

Plant Feature	Impact on Soil	Result
Root system	Loosening and aeration of the soil	Improved water and air exchange
Plant residues	Accumulation of organic matter	Increased humus content
Leguminous plants	Nitrogen fixation	Increased soil fertility
Vegetation cover	Soil protection	Reduced erosion

Material and methodology of the study

The research work is dedicated to the study of the mutual interactions existing between soil and vegetation cover. During the investigation, various scientific sources, monographs, and scientific articles were analyzed. The materials of the research consisted of scientific literature in the fields of soil science, botany, and ecology. Scientific works by various authors were studied comparatively, and existing theoretical approaches were systematized. Methods of analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, generalization, and systematization were utilized. These methods allowed for a clearer explanation of ecological and biological processes. Additionally, data regarding the role of plant residues, root systems, and microorganisms were analyzed. The research determined that vegetation cover is a vital factor in the soil formation process.

Discussion and results of the study

Investigations show that the interaction between soil and plants ensures the stability of natural ecosystems. Plants absorb water and minerals for development while influencing soil structure and

fertility. Plant residues increase the humus reserves of the soil. Humus is a fundamental factor in soil fertility. In soils rich in organic matter, intensive microorganism activity accelerates biological processes. The plant root system facilitates soil loosening, aeration, and improved water movement. Consequently, nutrient absorption becomes more efficient. Additionally, vegetation cover protects the soil from erosion. Plant roots bind soil particles together, preventing them from being washed away by the effects of wind and water [10]. This is critical in mountainous and semi-desert areas. Leguminous plants specifically increase nitrogen reserves through nitrogen-fixing bacteria. Overall, the interaction between soil and plants is a fundamental element of the cycle of matter in nature. Protecting this relationship is essential for sustainable agriculture and ecological balance.

Conclusions

The interaction between plants and soil is one of the primary conditions for the sustainability of ecosystems. Plants play a crucial role in preserving soil fertility, improving its structure, and preventing erosion processes. Soil, in turn, provides the water, minerals, and physical environment necessary for plant development. From the perspective of sustainable development, preserving the soil-plant relationship is of particular importance [1, p. 22–25; 4, p. 41–44; 5, p. 310–315].

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REFERENCES:

1. Aliyev T. Agrochemistry. Ganja: “AKTA”, 2004, 256 p.
2. Hajimammadov I.M., Kosayev E.M. Methods of agrochemical analysis of soil, plants and fertilizers. Baku: “Muallim”, 2016, 132 p.
3. Huseynov A.M., Huseynov N.V. Soil chemistry. Baku: “Qanun”, 2015, 584 p.
4. Huseynov A.M., Huseynov N.V., Mammadova K.Y. Agrochemistry (textbook for higher education institutions). Baku, 2018, 441 p.
5. Mammadov G. Fundamentals of soil science and soil geography. Baku: “Elm”, 2007, 383 p.
6. Mammadova S.Z., Jafarov A.B. Fertility property of soil. Baku: “Elm”, 2005, 194 p.
7. Seyidaliyev N. Fundamentals of agrochemistry. Baku: “Vektor”, 2016, 458 p.
8. Binomial nomenclature: https://az.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binominal_nomenklatura
9. Plants: <https://az.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bitkilər>
10. Soil: <https://az.wikipedia.org/wiki/Torpaq>